

Prioritisation analysis based on biodiversity variables

Deliverable 5.3

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The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 5.3 overview

This report presents results of preliminary prioritisation analysis based on species ranges on the MPA Europe project study area. It uses the species range maps (species distribution models, SDM) developed under the project WP3 (Species and Biogenic habitat Distribution (Principe et al., 2023; OBIS 2024)). Through this prioritization process, optimal MPA networks covering 10% and 30% of European seas will be identified for biodiversity, blue carbon, and their combined benefits.

Next steps will include validation and improvement of the SDM based on partners and stakeholders comments; inclusion of the conservation status and extinction risk of biological species, including information on non-indigenous species (Principe et al, 2024); prioritisation analyses under 5 different climate change scenarios (SSP1-SSP5) and two time periods (2050, 2100): and regional analyses accounting for marine regions, biogeographical regions and individual country marine domains.

*Disclaimer: Please be aware that this report presents results from preliminary analyses undertaken to illustrate the approach which will subsequently be used with a greater number of layers for Deliverables **D5.5** (Prioritisation analysis based on biodiversity variables and blue carbon) and **D5.7** (Online atlas for Marine Spatial Planning). We are currently validating the species and habitat distribution model outputs and will soon launch an optimized version of the range maps and the associated dashboard (<https://shiny.obis.org/distmaps>). In the meantime, we have explored the prioritisation based on a subset of the species maps, and results should not be used to draw final conclusions on the best locations for MPA networks. A final version of the prioritisation map based on all the available biodiversity data will be available for Deliverable D5.7 (Online atlas for Marine Spatial Planning).*

Introduction

European and international initiatives, such as [Biodiversity Strategy for 2030](#) (BDS, COM/2020/380 final) and [Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework](#) (GBF, CBD/COP/15/L25) adopted by the European Union and the Conference of Parties COP15 respectively, called for the protection of at least 30% of each marine habitat globally and at least 30% of all the ocean for worldwide effective marine biodiversity conservation by 2030. The Biodiversity Strategy also requests an additional commitment to strictly protect at least 10% of European seas. The MPA Europe project will identify the optimal places to protect marine biodiversity in an ecologically representative network.

A Marine Protected Area (MPA) network that is representative of the biodiversity in a region can be designed using evidence-based systematic conservation that uses decision-support tools such as *Zonation* (Moilanen et al., 2009). Previous studies both globally (e.g. Zhao et al., 2020) or nationally (e.g., Stephenson et al., 2023) have shown that a data-driven approach can identify the optimal locations for Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) in the most cost-effective way while minimizing the area covered. The benefits of effective MPAs include not only the protection of biodiversity, but also the restoration of ecosystems and fisheries, generating benefits for fisheries and ecotourism, and enhancing ecosystem resilience to climate change (Costello, 2024).

Methods

We used maps of the modelled ranges of 489 species (Appendix) previously selected for the MPA Europe Case Study with WWF Europe (WWF Europe, *in prep.*). The maps were obtained through species distribution models (SDM) developed previously by the project (Principe, 2023) and available online (<https://shiny.obis.org/distmaps>; OBIS, 2024). The raster layers had a spatial resolution of 0.05 degrees (*ca* 5 km) and were pre-processed with R packages *dpylr*, *terra*, and *arrow* to include uncertainty (i.e., using the uncertainty discounting approach described in Moilanen et al., 2006) and to mask the SDMs according to the MPA Europe study area. The prioritization analysis was performed with the software *Zonation 5 v1.0* (Moilanen et al., 2022) using default settings and the Core Area Zonation (CAZ1)¹ prioritisation algorithm which iteratively removes the cells that contribute least to the conservation objective.

Results

The results include a priority map, where each grid cell has been ranked from lowest to highest priority (Figure 1) and the top 10 % only (Figure 2). In the priority map the top ranked areas represent optimal areas that would include most species (Figures 1). In these results, coastal areas, and some off-shore sites (e.g., off Portugal, Ireland, Norway), were highly prioritised for protection.

The mean performance curve shows how many of the species can be included for a given area (Figure 3). In the top 10 % priority areas (Figure 2) (i.e., priority rank > 0.9) *ca* 70 % of the species were predicted to be represented (Figure 3). In the top 30 % priority areas, (i.e., priority rank > 0.7) *ca* 85 % of the species were predicted to be represented (Figure 3).

The histograms show the proportion of species' distributions in a given level (area) of priority (Figure 4). The 10-bar histogram plot (Figure 4) shows the proportion of species represented in the

¹ Core Area Zonation variant CAZ1 is one the new marginal loss rules available in Zonation v5. CAZ1 emphasizes high average coverage, even at the cost of reduced coverage of some features. For further details see the Moilanen et al. (2024). Zonation 5 v2.0 user manual. 206 pp

highest 30 % and 10 % priority areas for conservation. For most species, these areas cover more than 90 % of their predicted geographic range (peak in the histogram rightmost bar, 0.9-1.0).

Discussion

The purpose of this exploratory test was mainly to (1) identify if the current data being produced is fully conformant to *Zonation* needs, and (2) prepare and fine-tune the pipelines for the full prioritisation. Considering that this will include more than several thousand additional species, a well-developed pipeline is essential to achieve the expected results. Nevertheless and despite the sub dataset of biodiversity, the distribution of high ranked priority areas seems plausible with both coastal and off-shore areas identified. There are certain similarities (e.g. offshore Portugal, Ireland and Norway) and differences (e.g. Baltic Sea) with the global prioritisation performed by Zhao et al, 2020 (Figure 4) which included the AquaMaps (Kaschner et al., 2010) data set of > 24,000 species. However, AquaMaps was at a coarser spatial resolution and used a smaller number of species distribution records and selection of environmental variables than now available for Europe.

The > 12,000 SDMs are presently being validated and improved by assessing each modelling decision, comparing our results with other models, and inviting partners and stakeholders (Bramley et al, 2024a, 2024b; Bramley et al., *in prep*) to review the results and provide comments and/or suggestions. These include comments received during the last [MPA Europe North Atlantic Stakeholder Workshop](#) held on 18 February 2025 in Copenhagen. During this phase, improvements are expected as we implement alternative approaches and corrections.

Next steps

Next steps will include validation and improvement of the SDM based on partners and stakeholders comments; inclusion of the conservation status and extinction risk of biological species, including information on non-indigenous species (Principe et al, 2024); prioritisation analyses under 5 different climate change scenarios (SSP1-SSP5) and two time periods (2050, 2100): and regional analyses accounting for marine regions, biogeographical regions and individual country marine domains.

Further analyses will (a) use all of the 12,000 species range maps from OBIS, (b) positively weight species of conservation importance, (c) positively weight species that form biogenic habitats (e.g., seagrasses, maerl, kelp), and (d) include projected distributions of the species under future climate change scenarios. The results of these prioritisations will be compared with the recorded (not modelled) distributions of (1) biogenic habitats and (2) over 20,000 species without range maps but reported in European seas. Additional comparison with maps of human activities from EMODnet and other sources (e.g., fishery seabed trawling) will indicate how impacted the biodiversity in the prioritised areas may already be. Comparison with the Natura 2000 sites, and classification of MPA in a recent analysis, will indicate how well protected the prioritised areas, especially the top 10% of the area, may be.

Figure 1. Priority rank map based on 489 marine species range maps in European seas. Each grid cell has been ranked from lowest (blue) to highest (red) priority.

Figure 2. Top 10 % priority rank map based on 489 marine species range maps in European seas. Each grid cell has been ranked to highest (red) priority.

Figure 3. The prioritisation performance curve, showing that top 30 % (green dashed line) of the grid cells ranked from 0.7 to 1, and 10 % (red dashed line, grid cells ranked from 0.9 to 1) of the study area cover ca 85 % and 70 % of the 489 species, respectively.

Figure 4. Histograms of species inclusion in the specific prioritised area, summarizing the inclusion of species in the top 0.7 – 1.0 (top) and 0.9 – 1.0 (bottom) of the study area. This shows more than 90 % of species (more than 100 species) occur inside the best 30 % and 10 % areas.

Figure 5. Close-up view of priority ranking areas of European Seas. Extract of Figure 4 published in Zhao et al. (2020), representing the global distribution of the Prioritized Areas (the 30 % highest prioritized areas) for planning a global MPA network. The red colour scale represents the Prioritized Areas from the lowest (light red) to the highest (dark red) within the 30% highest prioritized areas

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Appendix

Figure A1. The classes of the 489 species included in this study.

Table A1. A classified list of the 489 species included in this study.

AphiaID	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species
Animalia						
100614	Acanthocephala	Palaeacanthocephala	Polymorphida	Polymorphidae	<i>Corynosoma</i>	<i>Corynosoma strumosum</i>
416516	Annelida	Clitellata	Enchytraeida	Enchytraeidae	<i>Fridericia</i>	<i>Fridericia bulbosa</i>
116953	Annelida	Clitellata	Rhynchobdellida	Piscicolidae	<i>Branchellion</i>	<i>Branchellion torpedinis</i>
147000	Annelida	Clitellata	Tubificida	Naididae	<i>Limnodriloides</i>	<i>Limnodriloides scandinavicus</i>
129826	Annelida	Polychaeta	Amphinomida	Amphinomidae	<i>Chloeia</i>	<i>Chloeia venusta</i>
130016	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Dorvilleidae	<i>Ophryotrocha</i>	<i>Ophryotrocha longidentata</i>
130059	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Eunice</i>	<i>Eunice oerstedii</i>
327815	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Eunice</i>	<i>Eunice woodwardi</i>
329255	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Marphysa</i>	<i>Marphysa mullawa</i>
1305582	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Eunicidae	<i>Paucibranchia</i>	<i>Paucibranchia fallax</i>
607395	Annelida	Polychaeta	Eunicida	Lumbrineridae	<i>Lumbrineris</i>	<i>Lumbrineris luciliae</i>
129872	Annelida	Polychaeta	NA	Arenicolidae	<i>Branchiomaldane</i>	<i>Branchiomaldane vincentii</i>
129889	Annelida	Polychaeta	NA	Capitellidae	<i>Mastobranchnus</i>	<i>Mastobranchnus trinchessii</i>
130325	Annelida	Polychaeta	NA	Maldanidae	<i>Praxillella</i>	<i>Praxillella lophoseta</i>
1052455	Annelida	Polychaeta	NA	Orbiniidae	<i>Scoloplos</i>	<i>Scoloplos typicus</i>
326622	Annelida	Polychaeta	NA	Paraonidae	<i>Aricidea</i>	<i>Aricidea tetrabranchnia</i>
130867	Annelida	Polychaeta	NA	Sabellariidae	<i>Sabellaria</i>	<i>Sabellaria spinulosa</i>
130981	Annelida	Polychaeta	NA	Scalibregmatidae	<i>Sclerobregma</i>	<i>Sclerobregma branchiatum</i>
129735	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Acoetidae	<i>Eupanthalis</i>	<i>Eupanthalis kinbergi</i>
130774	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	<i>Harmothoe</i>	<i>Harmothoe longisetis</i>
130802	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Polynoidae	<i>Lepidonotus</i>	<i>Lepidonotus tenuisetosus</i>
238203	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Myrianida</i>	<i>Myrianida dentalia</i>
248051	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Nudisyllis</i>	<i>Nudisyllis pulligera</i>
761606	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Opisthodonta</i>	<i>Opisthodonta longocirrata</i>
131340	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Parapionosyllis</i>	<i>Parapionosyllis minuta</i>
852814	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Pionosyllis</i>	<i>Pionosyllis nidrosiensis</i>
597722	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Prosphaerosyllis</i>	<i>Prosphaerosyllis chauseyensis</i>
389235	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Salvatoria</i>	<i>Salvatoria koorineclavata</i>
957073	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Sphaerosyllis</i>	<i>Sphaerosyllis tarquei</i>
131409	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Syllides</i>	<i>Syllides fulvus</i>
131422	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Syllis</i>	<i>Syllis columbretensis</i>
131470	Annelida	Polychaeta	Phyllodocida	Syllidae	<i>Xenosyllis</i>	<i>Xenosyllis scabra</i>
882440	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Dialychone</i>	<i>Dialychone arenicola</i>
130918	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Hypsicomus</i>	<i>Hypsicomus stichophthalmos</i>
130956	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Sabellidae	<i>Potamilla</i>	<i>Potamilla torelli</i>

AphiaID	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species
130992	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Filogranula</i>	<i>Filogranula gracilis</i>
131007	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Hydroides</i>	<i>Hydroides minax</i>
334341	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Paradexiospira</i>	<i>Paradexiospira (Spirorbides) vitrea</i>
334840	Annelida	Polychaeta	Sabellida	Serpulidae	<i>Spirorbis</i>	<i>Spirorbis (Spirorbis) inornatus</i>
131147	Annelida	Polychaeta	Spionida	Spionidae	<i>Polydora</i>	<i>Polydora limicola</i>
129787	Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Ampharetidae	<i>Amphicteis</i>	<i>Amphicteis sundevalli</i>
129989	Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Cirratulidae	<i>Ctenodrilus</i>	<i>Ctenodrilus serratus</i>
129981	Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Cirratulidae	<i>Timarete</i>	<i>Timarete filigera</i>
327267	Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Flabelligeridae	<i>Brada</i>	<i>Brada tzetlini</i>
130106	Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Flabelligeridae	<i>Flabelligera</i>	<i>Flabelligera infundibularis</i>
131479	Annelida	Polychaeta	Terebellida	Terebellidae	<i>Amphitrite</i>	<i>Amphitrite variabilis</i>
508315	Arthropoda	Arachnida	Sarcoptiformes	Phenopelopidae	<i>Eupelops</i>	<i>Eupelops occultus</i>
345486	Arthropoda	Branchiopoda	Anomopoda	Moinidae	<i>Moina</i>	<i>Moina micrura</i>
104521	Arthropoda	Copepoda	Calanoida	Diaixidae	<i>Diaixis</i>	<i>Diaixis hibernica</i>
362051	Arthropoda	Copepoda	Calanoida	Tharybidae	<i>Tharybis</i>	<i>Tharybis groenlandica</i>
106535	Arthropoda	Copepoda	Cyclopoida	Cyclopinidae	<i>Cyclopina</i>	<i>Cyclopina schneideri</i>
115530	Arthropoda	Copepoda	Harpacticoida	Ameiridae	<i>Ameiropsis</i>	<i>Ameiropsis brevicornis</i>
348966	Arthropoda	Copepoda	Harpacticoida	Arenopontiidae	<i>Arenopontia</i>	<i>Arenopontia subterranea</i>
116561	Arthropoda	Copepoda	Harpacticoida	Dactylopusiidae	<i>Dactylopusia</i>	<i>Dactylopusia tisboides</i>
116259	Arthropoda	Copepoda	Harpacticoida	Laophontidae	<i>Laophonte</i>	<i>Laophonte cornuta</i>
116322	Arthropoda	Copepoda	Harpacticoida	Laophontidae	<i>Pseudonychocamptus</i>	<i>Pseudonychocamptus proximus</i>
116347	Arthropoda	Copepoda	Harpacticoida	Leptastacidae	<i>Paraleptastacus</i>	<i>Paraleptastacus holsaticus</i>
115978	Arthropoda	Copepoda	Harpacticoida	Miraciidae	<i>Protosammotopa</i>	<i>Protosammotopa norvegica</i>
116777	Arthropoda	Copepoda	Harpacticoida	Miraciidae	<i>Stenhelia</i>	<i>Stenhelia (Delavalia) reflexa</i>
116204	Arthropoda	Copepoda	Harpacticoida	Nannopodidae	<i>Nannopus</i>	<i>Nannopus palustris</i>
150591	Arthropoda	Hexapoda	Coleoptera	Carabidae	<i>Anisodactylus</i>	<i>Anisodactylus poeciloides</i>
743764	Arthropoda	Hexapoda	Diptera	Canacidae	<i>Tethina</i>	<i>Tethina grisea</i>
426239	Arthropoda	Hexapoda	Diptera	Hybotidae	<i>Chersodromia</i>	<i>Chersodromia hirta</i>
477163	Arthropoda	Hexapoda	Hemiptera	Mesoveliidae	<i>Mesovelia</i>	<i>Mesovelia vittigera</i>
494324	Arthropoda	Hexapoda	Hemiptera	Saldidae	<i>Chiloxanthus</i>	<i>Chiloxanthus pilosus</i>
232012	Arthropoda	Hexapoda	NA	Isotomidae	<i>Archisotoma</i>	<i>Archisotoma besselsi</i>
101873	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Acanthonotozomatidae	<i>Acanthonotozoma</i>	<i>Acanthonotozoma inflatum</i>
101917	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Ampelisca</i>	<i>Ampelisca pseudospinimana</i>
101939	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Ampeliscidae	<i>Byblis</i>	<i>Byblis affinis</i>
101980	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Amphilochidae	<i>Gitanopsis</i>	<i>Gitanopsis inermis</i>
102522	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Aristiidae	<i>Aristias</i>	<i>Aristias neglectus</i>
101826	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Caprellidae	<i>Caprella</i>	<i>Caprella ciliata</i>
254654	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Caprellidae	<i>Caprella</i>	<i>Caprella dubia</i>

AphiaID	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species
101853	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Caprellidae	<i>Caprella</i>	<i>Caprella tuberculata</i>
101983	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Cyproideidae	<i>Peltocoxa</i>	<i>Peltocoxa brevirostris</i>
102134	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Dexaminidae	<i>Dexamine</i>	<i>Dexamine spiniventris</i>
103034	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Dulichiiidae	<i>Dulichia</i>	<i>Dulichia spinosissima</i>
1053401	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Epimeriidae	<i>Epimeria</i>	<i>Epimeria (Epimeria) tuberculata</i>
102237	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Eusiridae	<i>Rhachotropis</i>	<i>Rhachotropis leucophthalma</i>
236509	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Hyalidae	<i>Apohyale</i>	<i>Apohyale perieri</i>
236510	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Hyalidae	<i>Apohyale</i>	<i>Apohyale stebbingi</i>
236561	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Hyperiididae	<i>Hyperoche</i>	<i>Hyperoche mediterranea</i>
754208	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Liljeborgiidae	<i>Idunella</i>	<i>Idunella mollis</i>
102607	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Lysianassidae	<i>Lysianassa</i>	<i>Lysianassa insperata</i>
416570	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Lysianassidae	<i>Nannonyx</i>	<i>Nannonyx goesii</i>
102789	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Melitidae	<i>Allomelita</i>	<i>Allomelita pellucida</i>
236538	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Oedicerotidae	<i>Deflexilodes</i>	<i>Deflexilodes acutipes</i>
102914	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Oedicerotidae	<i>Perioculodes</i>	<i>Perioculodes aequimanus</i>
102935	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Oedicerotidae	<i>Westwoodilla</i>	<i>Westwoodilla megalops</i>
548442	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Pardaliscidae	<i>Halicoides</i>	<i>Halicoides synopiae</i>
102950	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Pardaliscidae	<i>Pardaliscella</i>	<i>Pardaliscella boeckii</i>
102388	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Photidae	<i>Photis</i>	<i>Photis tenuicornis</i>
103087	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Stegocephalidae	<i>Andaniexis</i>	<i>Andaniexis lupus</i>
103102	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Stegocephalidae	<i>Stegocephaloides</i>	<i>Stegocephaloides christianiensis</i>
103110	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Stenothoidae	<i>Hardametopa</i>	<i>Hardametopa nasuta</i>
102565	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Tryphosidae	<i>Gronella</i>	<i>Gronella groenlandica</i>
102617	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Tryphosidae	<i>Lysianella</i>	<i>Lysianella petalocera</i>
102772	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Tryphosidae	<i>Tryphosella</i>	<i>Tryphosella schneideri</i>
102561	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Uristidae	<i>Euonyx</i>	<i>Euonyx chelatus</i>
102589	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Amphipoda	Uristidae	<i>Ichnopus</i>	<i>Ichnopus spinicornis</i>
110466	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Bodotriidae	<i>Cumopsis</i>	<i>Cumopsis longipes</i>
156142	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Bodotriidae	<i>Iphinoe</i>	<i>Iphinoe maeotica</i>
110512	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Lampropidae	<i>Hemilamprops</i>	<i>Hemilamprops normani</i>
110539	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Nannastacidae	<i>Campylaspis</i>	<i>Campylaspis alba</i>
110561	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Nannastacidae	<i>Campylaspis</i>	<i>Campylaspis vitrea</i>
110565	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Nannastacidae	<i>Cumella</i>	<i>Cumella (Cumella) decipiens</i>
182495	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Cumacea	Nannastacidae	<i>Cumella</i>	<i>Cumella (Cumella) divisa</i>
107482	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Alpheidae	<i>Alpheus</i>	<i>Alpheus rapacida</i>
107490	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Alpheidae	<i>Synalpheus</i>	<i>Synalpheus gambarelloides</i>
107356	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Epialtidae	<i>Pisa</i>	<i>Pisa muscosa</i>
107626	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Palaemonidae	<i>Periclimenes</i>	<i>Periclimenes aegylios</i>

AphiaID	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species
240886	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Pandalidae	<i>Plesionika</i>	<i>Plesionika carinata</i>
442261	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Parthenopidae	<i>Distolambrus</i>	<i>Distolambrus maltzami</i>
442337	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Parthenopidae	<i>Spinolambrus</i>	<i>Spinolambrus macrochelos</i>
107376	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Polybiidae	<i>Bathynectes</i>	<i>Bathynectes longipes</i>
107385	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Polybiidae	<i>Liocarcinus</i>	<i>Liocarcinus bolivari</i>
225681	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Polychelidae	<i>Cardus</i>	<i>Cardus crucifer</i>
107681	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Processidae	<i>Processa</i>	<i>Processa acutirostris</i>
382932	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Scyllaridae	<i>Acantharctus</i>	<i>Acantharctus posteli</i>
1056507	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Sergestidae	<i>Phorcosergia</i>	<i>Phorcosergia bisulcata</i>
107116	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Solenoceridae	<i>Hymenopenaeus</i>	<i>Hymenopenaeus chacei</i>
107743	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Decapoda	Upogebiidae	<i>Upogebia</i>	<i>Upogebia tipica</i>
237853	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Euphausiacea	Euphausiidae	<i>Euphausia</i>	<i>Euphausia eximia</i>
118815	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Aegidae	<i>Aega</i>	<i>Aega bicarinata</i>
119023	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Arcturidae	<i>Astacilla</i>	<i>Astacilla intermedia</i>
118204	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Bopyridae	<i>Bopyroides</i>	<i>Bopyroides hippolytes</i>
118217	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Bopyridae	<i>Hemiarthrus</i>	<i>Hemiarthrus abdominalis</i>
256674	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Cirolanidae	<i>Natatolana</i>	<i>Natatolana hirtipes</i>
118888	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Cymothoidae	<i>Cymothoa</i>	<i>Cymothoa oestrum</i>
256837	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Cymothoidae	<i>Nerocila</i>	<i>Nerocila armata</i>
118522	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Dendrotionidae	<i>Dendrotion</i>	<i>Dendrotion setosum</i>
118580	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Desmosomatidae	<i>Oecidiobranthus</i>	<i>Oecidiobranthus nanseni</i>
118979	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Gnathiidae	<i>Caecognathia</i>	<i>Caecognathia abyssorum</i>
118986	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Gnathiidae	<i>Caecognathia</i>	<i>Caecognathia stygia</i>
118659	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Haploniscidae	<i>Haploniscus</i>	<i>Haploniscus foresti</i>
118688	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Ischnomesidae	<i>Heteromesus</i>	<i>Heteromesus frigidus</i>
264175	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Janiridae	<i>Jaera</i>	<i>Jaera (Jaera) forsmanni</i>
118756	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Munnidae	<i>Munna</i>	<i>Munna hanseni</i>
118609	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Munnopsidae	<i>Disconectes</i>	<i>Disconectes latirostris</i>
118619	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Munnopsidae	<i>Eurycope</i>	<i>Eurycope ipthima</i>
183209	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Munnopsidae	<i>Ilyarachna</i>	<i>Ilyarachna dubia</i>
118680	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Munnopsidae	<i>Ilyarachna</i>	<i>Ilyarachna torleivi</i>
118642	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Munnopsidae	<i>Tythocope</i>	<i>Tythocope megalura</i>
118926	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Isopoda	Sphaeromatidae	<i>Campecopea</i>	<i>Campecopea hirsuta</i>
459311	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Leptostraca	Nebaliidae	<i>Nebalia</i>	<i>Nebalia reboreadae</i>
119935	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Lophogastrida	Lophogastridae	<i>Lophogaster</i>	<i>Lophogaster subglaber</i>
119974	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Mysida	Mysidae	<i>Boreomysis</i>	<i>Boreomysis (Boreomysis) tridens</i>
120024	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Mysida	Mysidae	<i>Hemimysis</i>	<i>Hemimysis abyssicola</i>
120026	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Mysida	Mysidae	<i>Hemimysis</i>	<i>Hemimysis lamornae</i>

AphiaID	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species
120185	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Mysida	Mysidae	<i>Pseudomma</i>	<i>Pseudomma frigidum</i>
136308	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Tanaidacea	Apseudidae	<i>Leviapseudes</i>	<i>Leviapseudes segonzaci</i>
136357	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Tanaidacea	Colletteidae	<i>Leptognathiella</i>	<i>Leptognathiella spinicauda</i>
1296685	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Tanaidacea	Pseudotanaididae	<i>Pseudotanais</i>	<i>Pseudotanais falcicula</i>
416601	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Tanaidacea	Tanaididae	<i>Zeuxo</i>	<i>Zeuxo holdichi</i>
478765	Arthropoda	Malacostraca	Tanaidacea	Typhlotanidae	<i>Typhlotanais</i>	<i>Typhlotanais proctagon</i>
127786	Arthropoda	Ostracoda	Halocyprida	Halocyprididae	<i>Fellia</i>	<i>Fellia bicornis</i>
127708	Arthropoda	Ostracoda	Myodocopida	Cylindroleberididae	<i>Synasterope</i>	<i>Synasterope norvegica</i>
183270	Arthropoda	Ostracoda	Myodocopida	Cypridinidae	<i>Metavargula</i>	<i>Metavargula quintuplex</i>
127946	Arthropoda	Ostracoda	Podocopida	Bythocytheridae	<i>Pseudocythere</i>	<i>Pseudocythere caudata</i>
150521	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Ammotheidae	<i>Achelia</i>	<i>Achelia hispida</i>
134630	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Ascorhynchidae	<i>Eurycyde</i>	<i>Eurycyde hispida</i>
134640	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Austrodecidae	<i>Pantopipetta</i>	<i>Pantopipetta longituberculata</i>
134693	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Nymphonidae	<i>Nymphon</i>	<i>Nymphon laterospinum</i>
134719	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Phoxichilidiidae	<i>Anoplodactylus</i>	<i>Anoplodactylus maritimus</i>
240414	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Phoxichilidiidae	<i>Anoplodactylus</i>	<i>Anoplodactylus pycnosoma</i>
134730	Arthropoda	Pycnogonida	Pantopoda	Phoxichilidiidae	<i>Anoplodactylus</i>	<i>Anoplodactylus virescens</i>
106224	Arthropoda	Thecostraca	Balanomorpha	Balanidae	<i>Megabalanus</i>	<i>Megabalanus azoricus</i>
106208	Arthropoda	Thecostraca	Balanomorpha	Balanidae	<i>Solidobalanus</i>	<i>Solidobalanus fallax</i>
134798	Arthropoda	Thecostraca	NA	Peltogastridae	<i>Peltogaster</i>	<i>Peltogaster paguri</i>
534923	Arthropoda	Thecostraca	Scalpellomorpha	Scalpellidae	<i>Amigdoscalpellum</i>	<i>Amigdoscalpellum costellatum</i>
104052	Brachiopoda	Rhynchonellata	Rhynchonellida	Cryptoporidae	<i>Cryptopora</i>	<i>Cryptopora gnomon</i>
111070	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Beaniidae	<i>Beania</i>	<i>Beania hirtissima</i>
111129	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Bryocryptellidae	<i>Porella</i>	<i>Porella minuta</i>
111179	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Bugulidae	<i>Kinetoskias</i>	<i>Kinetoskias smitti</i>
111207	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Calloporidae	<i>Copidozoum</i>	<i>Copidozoum tenuirostre</i>
111228	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Calloporidae	<i>Tegella</i>	<i>Tegella unicornis</i>
472036	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Candidae	<i>Bugulopsis</i>	<i>Bugulopsis peachii</i>
111302	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Chlidiidae	<i>Chlidonia</i>	<i>Chlidonia pyriformis</i>
111323	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Cribrulinidae	<i>Puellina</i>	<i>Puellina bifida</i>
111373	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Flustridae	<i>Sarsiflustra</i>	<i>Sarsiflustra abyssicola</i>
111379	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Haplopomidae	<i>Haplopoma</i>	<i>Haplopoma graniferum</i>
111466	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Phidoloporidae	<i>Rhynchozoon</i>	<i>Rhynchozoon neapolitanum</i>
111085	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Smittinidae	<i>Pseudoflustra</i>	<i>Pseudoflustra hincksi</i>
111140	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Cheilostomatida	Umbonulidae	<i>Rhamphostomella</i>	<i>Rhamphostomella costata</i>
111652	Bryozoa	Gymnolaemata	Ctenostomatida	Farrellidae	<i>Farrella</i>	<i>Farrella repens</i>
111764	Bryozoa	Stenolaemata	Cyclostomatida	Tubuliporidae	<i>Tubulipora</i>	<i>Tubulipora phalangea</i>
103370	Chordata	Appendicularia	Copelata	Fritillariidae	<i>Appendicularia</i>	<i>Appendicularia sicula</i>

AphiaID	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species
103415	Chordata	Appendicularia	Copelata	Oikopleuridae	<i>Oikopleura</i>	<i>Oikopleura (Vexillaria) parva</i>
103626	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Polycitoridae	<i>Polycitor</i>	<i>Polycitor crystallinus</i>
103642	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Polyclinidae	<i>Aplidium</i>	<i>Aplidium densum</i>
103657	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Polyclinidae	<i>Aplidium</i>	<i>Aplidium ocellatum</i>
103673	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Aplousobranchia	Polyclinidae	<i>Polyclinella</i>	<i>Polyclinella azemai</i>
103751	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Phlebobranchia	Octacnemidae	<i>Dicopia</i>	<i>Dicopia antirrhinum</i>
103760	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Phlebobranchia	Perophoridae	<i>Perophora</i>	<i>Perophora multiclathrata</i>
250885	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Molgulidae	<i>Molgula</i>	<i>Molgula griffithsii</i>
103813	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Pyuridae	<i>Bathypyura</i>	<i>Bathypyura celata</i>
103874	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Styelidae	<i>Cnemidocarpa</i>	<i>Cnemidocarpa mollispina</i>
103876	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Styelidae	<i>Cnemidocarpa</i>	<i>Cnemidocarpa platybranchia</i>
103927	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Styelidae	<i>Styela</i>	<i>Styela chaini</i>
103934	Chordata	Ascidiacea	Stolidobranchia	Styelidae	<i>Styela</i>	<i>Styela loculosa</i>
126275	Chordata	Chondrostei	Acipenseriformes	Acipenseridae	<i>Acipenser</i>	<i>Acipenser gueldenstaedtii</i>
105818	Chordata	Elasmobranchii	Carcharhiniformes	Sphyrnidae	<i>Sphyrna</i>	<i>Sphyrna tudes</i>
105852	Chordata	Elasmobranchii	Myliobatiformes	Dasyatidae	<i>Dasyatis</i>	<i>Dasyatis tortonesei</i>
105904	Chordata	Elasmobranchii	Squaliformes	Centrolophidae	<i>Deania</i>	<i>Deania hystricosa</i>
101171	Chordata	Myxini	Myxiniiformes	Myxinidae	<i>Myxine</i>	<i>Myxine ios</i>
314780	Chordata	Teleostei	Anguilliformes	Congridae	<i>Leptocephalus</i>	<i>Leptocephalus giganteus</i>
126312	Chordata	Teleostei	Anguilliformes	Ophichthidae	<i>Apterichthys</i>	<i>Apterichthys caecus</i>
761426	Chordata	Teleostei	Atheriniformes	Atherinidae	<i>Atherinomorus</i>	<i>Atherinomorus forskalii</i>
236454	Chordata	Teleostei	Aulopiformes	Paralepididae	<i>Paralepis</i>	<i>Paralepis speciosa</i>
126969	Chordata	Teleostei	<i>Eupercaria incertae sedis</i>	Labridae	<i>Lappanella</i>	<i>Lappanella fasciata</i>
277998	Chordata	Teleostei	<i>Eupercaria incertae sedis</i>	Labridae	<i>Oxycheilinus</i>	<i>Oxycheilinus mentalis</i>
126470	Chordata	Teleostei	Gadiformes	Macrouridae	<i>Gadomus</i>	<i>Gadomus dispar</i>
126871	Chordata	Teleostei	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	<i>Buenia</i>	<i>Buenia affinis</i>
126875	Chordata	Teleostei	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	<i>Chromogobius</i>	<i>Chromogobius zebratus</i>
275715	Chordata	Teleostei	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	<i>Microgobius</i>	<i>Microgobius erectus</i>
1022561	Chordata	Teleostei	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	<i>Proterorhinus</i>	<i>Proterorhinus semilunaris</i>
126938	Chordata	Teleostei	Gobiiformes	Gobiidae	<i>Thorogobius</i>	<i>Thorogobius macrolepis</i>
475090	Chordata	Teleostei	Kurtiformes	Apogonidae	<i>Apogonichthyooides</i>	<i>Apogonichthyooides pharaonis</i>
218650	Chordata	Teleostei	Mulliformes	Mullidae	<i>Mulloidichthys</i>	<i>Mulloidichthys pfluegeri</i>
126676	Chordata	Teleostei	Ophidiiformes	Ophidiidae	<i>Ophidion</i>	<i>Ophidion rochei</i>
218058	Chordata	Teleostei	Perciformes	Scorpaenidae	<i>Iracundus</i>	<i>Iracundus signifer</i>
281212	Chordata	Teleostei	Pleuronectiformes	Pleuronectidae	<i>Kareius</i>	<i>Kareius bicoloratus</i>
126786	Chordata	Teleostei	Scombriformes	Bramidae	<i>Taractes</i>	<i>Taractes asper</i>
126787	Chordata	Teleostei	Scombriformes	Bramidae	<i>Taractes</i>	<i>Taractes rubescens</i>
276360	Chordata	Teleostei	Scombriformes	Chiasmodontidae	<i>Dysalotus</i>	<i>Dysalotus oligoscolus</i>

AphiaID	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species
158727	Chordata	Teleostei	Stomiiformes	Stomiidae	<i>Eustomias</i>	<i>Eustomias lipochirus</i>
275163	Chordata	Teleostei	Stomiiformes	Stomiidae	<i>Melanostomias</i>	<i>Melanostomias margaritifera</i>
100972	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Andvakiidae	<i>Telmatactis</i>	<i>Telmatactis forskalii</i>
100889	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Edwardsiidae	<i>Edwardsia</i>	<i>Edwardsia longicornis</i>
100977	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Actiniaria	Kadosactinidae	<i>Kadosactis</i>	<i>Kadosactis rosea</i>
103309	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Antipatharia	Antipathidae	<i>Antipathes</i>	<i>Antipathes dichotoma</i>
283789	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Ceriantharia	Arachnactidae	<i>Isarachnanthus</i>	<i>Isarachnanthus maderensis</i>
135133	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Caryophylliidae	<i>Caryophyllia</i>	<i>Caryophyllia (Caryophyllia) abyssorum</i>
135134	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Caryophylliidae	<i>Caryophyllia</i>	<i>Caryophyllia (Caryophyllia) alberti</i>
135143	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Caryophylliidae	<i>Caryophyllia</i>	<i>Caryophyllia (Caryophyllia) seguenzae</i>
1245747	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Caryophylliidae	<i>Desmophyllum</i>	<i>Desmophyllum pertusum</i>
135168	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Caryophylliidae	<i>Solenosmilia</i>	<i>Solenosmilia variabilis</i>
135187	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Dendrophylliidae	<i>Dendrophyllia</i>	<i>Dendrophyllia ramea</i>
135203	Cnidaria	Hexacorallia	Scleractinia	Fungiacyathidae	<i>Fungiacyathus</i>	<i>Fungiacyathus (Bathyactis) crispus</i>
117778	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Anthoathecata	Pandaeidae	<i>Amphinema</i>	<i>Amphinema dinema</i>
117281	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Aglaopheniidae	<i>Aglaopenia</i>	<i>Aglaopenia parvula</i>
182727	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Haleciidae	<i>Halecium</i>	<i>Halecium plumosum</i>
117632	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Halopterididae	<i>Halopteris</i>	<i>Halopteris diaphana</i>
117900	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Sertularellidae	<i>Sertularella</i>	<i>Sertularella fusiformis</i>
117879	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Sertulariidae	<i>Diphasia</i>	<i>Diphasia fallax</i>
117971	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Leptothecata	Tiarannidae	<i>Stegolaria</i>	<i>Stegolaria geniculata</i>
135494	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Siphonophorae	Agalmatidae	<i>Marrus</i>	<i>Marrus orthocanna</i>
135458	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Siphonophorae	Prayidae	<i>Desmophyes</i>	<i>Desmophyes villafrancae</i>
117866	Cnidaria	Hydrozoa	Trachymedusae	Rhopalonematidae	<i>Sminthea</i>	<i>Sminthea arctica</i>
125380	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Acanthogorgiidae	<i>Bebryce</i>	<i>Bebryce mollis</i>
1116761	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Malacalcyonacea	Victorgorgiidae	<i>Trachythela</i>	<i>Trachythela rudis</i>
125373	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Keratoisididae	<i>Isidella</i>	<i>Isidella elongata</i>
125374	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Keratoisididae	<i>Isidella</i>	<i>Isidella lofotensis</i>
125409	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Primnoidae	<i>Narella</i>	<i>Narella versluysi</i>
125410	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Primnoidae	<i>Paracalyptrophora</i>	<i>Paracalyptrophora josephinae</i>
128525	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Protoptilidae	<i>Protoptilum</i>	<i>Protoptilum carpenterii</i>
286030	Cnidaria	Octocorallia	Scleralcyonacea	Sarcodictyonidae	<i>Sarcodictyon</i>	<i>Sarcodictyon catenatum</i>
888452	Cnidaria	Scyphozoa	Coronatae	Nausithoidae	<i>Nausithoe</i>	<i>Nausithoe simplex</i>
766645	Cnidaria	Scyphozoa	Rhizostomeae	Cepheidae	<i>Marivagia</i>	<i>Marivagia stellata</i>
135323	Cnidaria	Staurozoa	Stauromedusae	Haliclystidae	<i>Haliclystus</i>	<i>Haliclystus octoradiatus</i>
213117	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Paxillosida	Luidiidae	<i>Luidia</i>	<i>Luidia savignyi</i>

AphiaID	Phylum	Class	Order	Family	Genus	Species
123989	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Asterinidae	<i>Asterina</i>	<i>Asterina pancerii</i>
367763	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Mithrodiidae	<i>Thromidia</i>	<i>Thromidia catalai</i>
125168	Echinodermata	Asteroidea	Valvatida	Poraniidae	<i>Culcitopsis</i>	<i>Culcitopsis borealis</i>
213601	Echinodermata	Crinoidea	Comatulida	Mariametridae	<i>Dichrometra</i>	<i>Dichrometra flagellata</i>
124441	Echinodermata	Holothuroidea	Apodida	Myriotrochidae	<i>Myriotrochus</i>	<i>Myriotrochus (Oligotrochus) bathybius</i>
124672	Echinodermata	Holothuroidea	Dendrochirotida	Phylloporidae	<i>Thyone</i>	<i>Thyone inermis</i>
183321	Echinodermata	Holothuroidea	Synallactida	Synallactidae	<i>Paelopatides</i>	<i>Paelopatides gigantea</i>
412703	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	<i>Acrocrida</i>	<i>Acrocrida spatulispina</i>
125066	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Amphiuridae	<i>Amphipholis</i>	<i>Amphipholis torelli</i>
124908	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Amphilepidida	Hemieuryalidae	<i>Ophiozonella</i>	<i>Ophiozonella molesta</i>
124983	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiacanthida	Ophiacanthidae	<i>Ophiacantha</i>	<i>Ophiacantha crassidens</i>
124994	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiacanthida	Ophiacanthidae	<i>Ophiacantha</i>	<i>Ophiacantha mesembria</i>
125004	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiacanthida	Ophiacanthidae	<i>Ophiacantha</i>	<i>Ophiacantha smitti</i>
125145	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiacanthida	Ophiomyxidae	<i>Ophiomyxa</i>	<i>Ophiomyxa serpentaria</i>
124837	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiurida	NA	<i>Anthophiura</i>	<i>Anthophiura ingolfi</i>
322555	Echinodermata	Ophiuroidea	Ophiurida	Ophiuridae	<i>Ophiura</i>	<i>Ophiura saurura</i>
138783	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcida	Arcidae	<i>Anadara</i>	<i>Anadara corbuloides</i>
138798	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Arcida	Arcidae	<i>Bathyarca</i>	<i>Bathyarca inaequisculpta</i>
138994	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Cardiidae	<i>Acanthocardia</i>	<i>Acanthocardia spinosa</i>
181344	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Cardiidae	<i>Parvicardium</i>	<i>Parvicardium vroomi</i>
156227	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Cardiida	Tellinidae	<i>Macoma</i>	<i>Macoma torelli</i>
138817	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Carditida	Astartidae	<i>Astarte</i>	<i>Astarte arctica</i>
423186	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Galeommatida	Lasaeidae	<i>Boreacola</i>	<i>Boreacola maltzani</i>
237848	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Galeommatida	Lasaeidae	<i>Coracuta</i>	<i>Coracuta obliquata</i>
141598	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Myida	Teredinidae	<i>Bankia</i>	<i>Bankia carinata</i>
141605	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Myida	Teredinidae	<i>Teredo</i>	<i>Teredo bartschi</i>
140450	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytilida	Mytilidae	<i>Dacrydium</i>	<i>Dacrydium viviparum</i>
140480	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytilida	Mytilidae	<i>Mytilus</i>	<i>Mytilus edulis</i>
140481	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Mytilida	Mytilidae	<i>Mytilus</i>	<i>Mytilus galloprovincialis</i>
507047	Mollusca	Bivalvia	NA	Parilimyidae	<i>Parilimyia</i>	<i>Parilimyia loveni</i>
183374	Mollusca	Bivalvia	NA	Protocuspidariidae	<i>Protocuspidaria</i>	<i>Protocuspidaria verityi</i>
403944	Mollusca	Bivalvia	NA	Verticordiidae	<i>Spinospella</i>	<i>Spinospella acuticostata</i>
141993	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Nuculanida	Yoldiidae	<i>Yoldiella</i>	<i>Yoldiella dissimilis</i>
506699	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Ostreida	Ostreidae	<i>Alectryonella</i>	<i>Alectryonella plicatula</i>
140658	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Ostreida	Ostreidae	<i>Ostrea</i>	<i>Ostrea edulis</i>
140686	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pectinida	Pectinidae	<i>Aequipecten</i>	<i>Aequipecten commutatus</i>
141551	Mollusca	Bivalvia	Pectinida	Spondylidae	<i>Spondylus</i>	<i>Spondylus senegalensis</i>

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140853	Mollusca	Caudofoveata	Chaetodermatida	Prochaetodermatidae	<i>Prochaetoderma</i>	<i>Prochaetoderma yongei</i>
341792	Mollusca	Cephalopoda	Oegopsida	Brachioteuthidae	<i>Brachioteuthis</i>	<i>Brachioteuthis beanii</i>
139074	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Caenogastropoda <i>incertae sedis</i>	Cerithiopsidae	<i>Cerithiopsis</i>	<i>Cerithiopsis barleei</i>
139078	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Caenogastropoda <i>incertae sedis</i>	Cerithiopsidae	<i>Cerithiopsis</i>	<i>Cerithiopsis jeffreysi</i>
139554	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Cephalaspidea	Diaphanidae	<i>Diaphana</i>	<i>Diaphana lactea</i>
1342949	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Cephalaspidea	Haminoeidae	<i>Weinkauffia</i>	<i>Weinkauffia macandrewii</i>
140742	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Cephalaspidea	Laonidae	<i>Laona</i>	<i>Laona pruinosa</i>
140743	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Cephalaspidea	Philinidae	<i>Philine</i>	<i>Philine angulata</i>
153527	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Cephalaspidea	Retusidae	<i>Retusa</i>	<i>Retusa nitidula</i>
139966	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Lepetellida	Fissurellidae	<i>Emarginula</i>	<i>Emarginula sicula</i>
216869	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Cypraeidae	<i>Mauritia</i>	<i>Mauritia grayana</i>
138678	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Eulimidae	<i>Aclis</i>	<i>Aclis ascaris</i>
419710	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Hipponicidae	<i>Hipponix</i>	<i>Hipponix incurvus</i>
140524	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Naticidae	<i>Bulbus</i>	<i>Bulbus smithii</i>
140667	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Ovulidae	<i>Pseudosimnia</i>	<i>Pseudosimnia carnea</i>
141222	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Rissoidae	<i>Alvania</i>	<i>Alvania pagodula</i>
141360	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Rissoidae	<i>Rissoa</i>	<i>Rissoa monodonta</i>
141896	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Littorinimorpha	Velutinidae	<i>Onchidiopsis</i>	<i>Onchidiopsis glacialis</i>
215426	Mollusca	Gastropoda	NA	Aplustridae	<i>Hydatina</i>	<i>Hydatina zonata</i>
139162	Mollusca	Gastropoda	NA	Cimidae	<i>Cima</i>	<i>Cima minima</i>
420565	Mollusca	Gastropoda	NA	Oxynoidae	<i>Lobiger</i>	<i>Lobiger souverbii</i>
456662	Mollusca	Gastropoda	NA	Patellidae	<i>Cymbula</i>	<i>Cymbula safiana</i>
491654	Mollusca	Gastropoda	NA	Pyramidellidae	<i>Brachystomia</i>	<i>Brachystomia carrozzai</i>
140970	Mollusca	Gastropoda	NA	Pyramidellidae	<i>Menestho</i>	<i>Menestho truncatula</i>
141017	Mollusca	Gastropoda	NA	Pyramidellidae	<i>Odostomia</i>	<i>Odostomia striolata</i>
836215	Mollusca	Gastropoda	NA	Pyramidellidae	<i>Pyrgiscus</i>	<i>Pyrgiscus jeffreysii</i>
836210	Mollusca	Gastropoda	NA	Pyramidellidae	<i>Pyrgostylus</i>	<i>Pyrgostylus striatulus</i>
140275	Mollusca	Gastropoda	NA	Rhodopetalidae	<i>Erginus</i>	<i>Erginus rubellus</i>
138870	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Buccinidae	<i>Buccinum</i>	<i>Buccinum nivale</i>
138888	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Chauvetiidae	<i>Chauvetia</i>	<i>Chauvetia procerula</i>
138892	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Chauvetiidae	<i>Chauvetia</i>	<i>Chauvetia turritellata</i>
139200	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Columbellidae	<i>Mitrella</i>	<i>Mitrella minor</i>
511794	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Columbellidae	<i>Strombina</i>	<i>Strombina maculosa</i>
835892	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Conidae	<i>Conasprella</i>	<i>Conasprella centurio</i>
957141	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Costellariidae	<i>Pusia</i>	<i>Pusia granum</i>
1396112	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Costellariidae	<i>Pusia</i>	<i>Pusia zebrina</i>

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434357	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Mangeliidae	<i>Mangelia</i>	<i>Mangelia stosiciana</i>
208283	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Mitridae	<i>Pterygia</i>	<i>Pterygia scabricula</i>
407837	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Muricidae	<i>Murexsul</i>	<i>Murexsul aradasii</i>
1115499	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Nassariidae	<i>Tritia</i>	<i>Tritia lima</i>
139248	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Raphitomidae	<i>Gymnobela</i>	<i>Gymnobela frielei</i>
195916	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Raphitomidae	<i>Leufroyia</i>	<i>Leufroyia concinna</i>
139381	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Neogastropoda	Raphitomidae	<i>Taranis</i>	<i>Taranis borealis</i>
531091	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Aegiridae	<i>Notodoris</i>	<i>Notodoris serенаe</i>
138714	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Aeolidiidae	<i>Aeolidiella</i>	<i>Aeolidiella sanguinea</i>
139431	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Cumanotidae	<i>Cumanotus</i>	<i>Cumanotus beaumonti</i>
139645	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Dotidae	<i>Doto</i>	<i>Doto lemchei</i>
225518	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Nudibranchia	Myrrhinidae	<i>Godiva</i>	<i>Godiva quadricolor</i>
140811	Mollusca	Gastropoda	Pleurobranchida	Pleurobranchidae	<i>Berthella</i>	<i>Berthella ocellata</i>
724146	Mollusca	Polyplacophora	Chitonida	Chitonidae	<i>Rhyssofax</i>	<i>Rhyssofax canaliculata</i>
1288184	Mollusca	Polyplacophora	Chitonida	Chitonidae	<i>Rhyssofax</i>	<i>Rhyssofax corallina</i>
140387	Mollusca	Polyplacophora	Chitonida	Mopaliidae	<i>Placiphorella</i>	<i>Placiphorella atlantica</i>
140001	Mollusca	Scaphopoda	Gadilida	Gadilidae	<i>Cadulus</i>	<i>Cadulus artatus</i>
140002	Mollusca	Scaphopoda	Gadilida	Gadilidae	<i>Cadulus</i>	<i>Cadulus cylindricus</i>
139610	Mollusca	Solenogastres	NA	Dondersiidae	<i>Nematomenia</i>	<i>Nematomenia banyulensis</i>
140561	Mollusca	Solenogastres	NA	Neomeniidae	<i>Neomenia</i>	<i>Neomenia dalyelli</i>
121326	Nematoda	Chromadorea	Araeolaimida	Axonolaimidae	<i>Odontophora</i>	<i>Odontophora longisetosa</i>
121352	Nematoda	Chromadorea	Araeolaimida	Comesomatidae	<i>Laimella</i>	<i>Laimella longicauda</i>
121189	Nematoda	Chromadorea	Desmoscolecida	Cyartoneumatidae	<i>Cyartoneuma</i>	<i>Cyartoneuma germanicum</i>
121484	Nematoda	Chromadorea	Monhysterida	Sphaerolaimidae	<i>Sphaerolaimus</i>	<i>Sphaerolaimus balticus</i>
121592	Nematoda	Chromadorea	Monhysterida	Xyalidae	<i>Rhynchonema</i>	<i>Rhynchonema lyngei</i>
153445	Nematoda	Chromadorea	Monhysterida	Xyalidae	<i>Rhynchonema</i>	<i>Rhynchonema quemer</i>
121601	Nematoda	Chromadorea	Monhysterida	Xyalidae	<i>Theristus</i>	<i>Theristus acer</i>
121302	Nematoda	Chromadorea	Plectida	Tubolaimoididae	<i>Tubolaimoides</i>	<i>Tubolaimoides tenuicaudatus</i>
121763	Nematoda	Enoplea	Enoplida	Anoplostomatidae	<i>Anoplostoma</i>	<i>Anoplostoma viviparum</i>
122768	Nemertea	Hoploneurata	Monostilifera	Tetrastemmatidae	<i>Tetrastemma</i>	<i>Tetrastemma coronatum</i>
122635	Nemertea	Palaeonemertea	Tubulaniformes	Tubulanidae	<i>Tubulanus</i>	<i>Tubulanus nothus</i>
122490	Nemertea	Pilidiophora	Heteronemertea	Lineidae	<i>Cerebratulus</i>	<i>Cerebratulus ventrosulcatus</i>
132252	Porifera	Calcarea	Leucosolenida	Syconidae	<i>Sycon</i>	<i>Sycon elegans</i>
164607	Porifera	Calcarea	Leucosolenida	Syconidae	<i>Sycon</i>	<i>Sycon quadrangulatum</i>
134145	Porifera	Demospongiae	Clionaida	Clionaidae	<i>Cliona</i>	<i>Cliona vermifera</i>
132349	Porifera	Demospongiae	Dictyoceratida	Irciniidae	<i>Ircinia</i>	<i>Ircinia dendroides</i>
165122	Porifera	Demospongiae	Dictyoceratida	Spongiidae	<i>Hyattella</i>	<i>Hyattella cavernosa</i>
132761	Porifera	Demospongiae	Haplosclerida	Chalinidae	<i>Chalinula</i>	<i>Chalinula limbata</i>

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132762	Porifera	Demospongiae	Haplosclerida	Chalinidae	<i>Chalinula</i>	<i>Chalinula loosanoffi</i>
132768	Porifera	Demospongiae	Haplosclerida	Chalinidae	<i>Dendroxea</i>	<i>Dendroxea lenis</i>
132883	Porifera	Demospongiae	Haplosclerida	Chalinidae	<i>Haliclona</i>	<i>Haliclona (Soestella) xena</i>
133192	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Cladorhizidae	<i>Cladorhiza</i>	<i>Cladorhiza gelida</i>
169049	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Crellidae	<i>Crella</i>	<i>Crella (Crella) elegans</i>
133620	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Hymedesmiidae	<i>Hymedesmia</i>	<i>Hymedesmia (Hymedesmia) pansa</i>
167852	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Microcionidae	<i>Antho</i>	<i>Antho (Acarnia) coriacea</i>
168526	Porifera	Demospongiae	Poecilosclerida	Mycalidae	<i>Mycale</i>	<i>Mycale (Aegogropila) contarenii</i>
132655	Porifera	Demospongiae	Suberitida	Halichondriidae	<i>Hymeniacidon</i>	<i>Hymeniacidon kitchingi</i>
170786	Porifera	Demospongiae	Suberitida	Suberitidae	<i>Protosuberites</i>	<i>Protosuberites epiphytum</i>
134105	Porifera	Demospongiae	Tetractinellida	Theneidae	<i>Thenea</i>	<i>Thenea levis</i>
169724	Porifera	Homoscleromorpha	Homosclerophorida	Oscarellidae	<i>Oscarella</i>	<i>Oscarella tuberculata</i>
101157	Priapulida	NA	Priapulomorpha	Priapulidae	<i>Priapulopsis</i>	<i>Priapulopsis bicaudatus</i>
248010	Rotifera	Eurotatoria	Ploima	Brachionidae	<i>Keratella</i>	<i>Keratella tropica</i>
148328	Rotifera	Eurotatoria	Ploima	Lecanidae	<i>Lecane</i>	<i>Lecane closterocerca</i>
135057	Rotifera	Eurotatoria	Ploima	Synchaetidae	<i>Synchaeta</i>	<i>Synchaeta littoralis</i>
Chromista						
394949	Cercozoa	Ascetosporea	Haplosporida	Haplosporidiidae	<i>Haplosporidium</i>	<i>Haplosporidium nelsoni</i>
590938	Cercozoa	Metromonadea	Metromonadida	NA	<i>Micrometopion</i>	<i>Micrometopion nutans</i>
341712	Ciliophora	Litostomatea	Haptorida	Didiniidae	<i>Didinium</i>	<i>Didinium gargantua</i>
427070	Ciliophora	Oligohymenophorea	Philasterida	Pseudocohnilembidae	<i>Pseudocohnilembus</i>	<i>Pseudocohnilembus hargisi</i>
417147	Ciliophora	Oligotrichea	Choreotrichida	Codonellidae	<i>Tintinnopsis</i>	<i>Tintinnopsis dadayi</i>
235762	Ciliophora	Oligotrichea	Choreotrichida	Epiplocyloidae	<i>Epiplocytilis</i>	<i>Epiplocytilis acuminata</i>
417212	Ciliophora	Oligotrichea	Choreotrichida	Eutintinnidae	<i>Eutintinnus</i>	<i>Eutintinnus macilentus</i>
427479	Ciliophora	Oligotrichea	Choreotrichida	Metacyclidae	<i>Coxiella</i>	<i>Coxiella annulata</i>
427559	Ciliophora	Oligotrichea	Choreotrichida	Tintinnidae	<i>Salpingella</i>	<i>Salpingella curta</i>
101301	Ciliophora	Oligotrichea	Oligotrichida	Strombidiidae	<i>Strombidium</i>	<i>Strombidium oblongum</i>
172363	Ciliophora	Phyllopharyngea	Exogenida	Ephelotidae	<i>Ephelota</i>	<i>Ephelota gemmipara</i>
417103	Ciliophora	Spirotrichea	Euplotida	Aspidiscidae	<i>Aspidisca</i>	<i>Aspidisca magna</i>
427701	Ciliophora	Spirotrichea	Euplotida	Uronychiidae	<i>Paradiophrys</i>	<i>Paradiophrys irmgard</i>
427710	Ciliophora	Spirotrichea	Kiitrichida	Kiitrichidae	<i>Caryotricha</i>	<i>Caryotricha minuta</i>
427713	Ciliophora	Spirotrichea	Licnophorida	Licnophoridae	<i>Licnophora</i>	<i>Licnophora lyngbycola</i>
427893	Ciliophora	Spirotrichea	NA	Holostichidae	<i>Psammomitra</i>	<i>Psammomitra retractilis</i>
427894	Ciliophora	Spirotrichea	NA	Holostichidae	<i>Pseudoamphisiella</i>	<i>Pseudoamphisiella alveolata</i>
641230	Cryptophyta	Cryptophyceae	Cryptomonadales	Cryptomonadaceae	<i>Cryptomonas</i>	<i>Cryptomonas kielensis</i>
736527	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Lituolida	Ammosphaeroidinidae	<i>Cribrostomoides</i>	<i>Cribrostomoides sphaerilocula</i>
114058	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Lituolida	Ammosphaeroidinidae	<i>Recurvoides</i>	<i>Recurvoides turbinatus</i>
113694	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Robertinida	Robertinidae	<i>Robertinoides</i>	<i>Robertinoides pumilum</i>

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1470603	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Anomalinidae	<i>Anomalinoides</i>	<i>Anomalinoides spissiformis</i>
112959	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Cancrisidae	<i>Valvulineria</i>	<i>Valvulineria arctica</i>
1035156	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Catapsydracidae	<i>Subbotina</i>	<i>Subbotina trilocolinoides</i>
113356	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Eponididae	<i>Eponides</i>	<i>Eponides repandus</i>
735514	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Gavelinellidae	<i>Gavelinella</i>	<i>Gavelinella beccariiiformis</i>
735117	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Globigerinidae	<i>Globigerina</i>	<i>Globigerina eamesi</i>
735120	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Globigerinidae	<i>Globigerina</i>	<i>Globigerina foliata</i>
1290592	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Globigerinidae	<i>Globigerinoides</i>	<i>Globigerinoides altiapertura</i>
1026816	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Globoquadrinidae	<i>Dentoglobigerina</i>	<i>Dentoglobigerina galavisi</i>
1347368	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Globorotaliidae	<i>Fohsella</i>	<i>Fohsella linguaensis</i>
1026408	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Globorotaliidae	<i>Globoconella</i>	<i>Globoconella conoidea</i>
895702	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Globorotaliidae	<i>Globorotalia</i>	<i>Globorotalia archeomenardii</i>
735297	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Heterohelicidae	<i>Pseudotextularia</i>	<i>Pseudotextularia elegans</i>
905534	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Nonionidae	<i>Nonion</i>	<i>Nonion havanense</i>
113182	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Rosalinidae	<i>Rosalina</i>	<i>Rosalina williamsoni</i>
113184	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Rosalinidae	<i>Tretomphalus</i>	<i>Tretomphalus bulloides</i>
1027637	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Truncorotaloididae	<i>Acarinina</i>	<i>Acarinina rohri</i>
735243	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Truncorotaloididae	<i>Morozovella</i>	<i>Morozovella angulata</i>
1027877	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Truncorotaloididae	<i>Morozovella</i>	<i>Morozovella subbotinae</i>
113760	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Rotaliida	Uvigerinidae	<i>Trifarina</i>	<i>Trifarina fornasinii</i>
114261	Foraminifera	Globothalamea	Textulariida	Textulariidae	<i>Siphotextularia</i>	<i>Siphotextularia rolshauseni</i>
113879	Foraminifera	Monothalamea	Astrorhizida	Hippocrepinidae	<i>Jaculella</i>	<i>Jaculella acuta</i>
113909	Foraminifera	Monothalamea	Astrorhizida	Vanhoeffenellidae	<i>Vanhoeffenella</i>	<i>Vanhoeffenella gaussi</i>
736676	Foraminifera	Nodosariata	NA	Reophacidae	<i>Leptohalysis</i>	<i>Leptohalysis catella</i>
113784	Foraminifera	Nodosariata	Vaginulinida	Vaginulinidae	<i>Lenticulina</i>	<i>Lenticulina calcar</i>
480146	Foraminifera	Nodosariata	Vaginulinida	Vaginulinidae	<i>Marginulina</i>	<i>Marginulina similis</i>
112588	Foraminifera	Tubothalamea	Miliolida	Hauerinidae	<i>Pyrgo</i>	<i>Pyrgo elongata</i>
115129	Haptophyta	Coccolithophyceae	Prymnesiales	Chrysochromulinaceae	<i>Chrysochromulina</i>	<i>Chrysochromulina spinifera</i>
180183	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Anaulales	Anaulaceae	<i>Eunotogramma</i>	<i>Eunotogramma laevis</i>
964394	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Biddulphiales	Biddulphiaceae	<i>Biddulphia</i>	<i>Biddulphia mobiliensis</i>
163133	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Chaetocerotanae <i>incertae sedis</i>	Chaetocerotaceae	<i>Chaetoceros</i>	<i>Chaetoceros abnormis</i>
149299	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Chaetocerotanae <i>incertae sedis</i>	Chaetocerotaceae	<i>Chaetoceros</i>	<i>Chaetoceros armatus</i>
176171	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Cymbellales	Gomphonemataceae	<i>Gomphonema</i>	<i>Gomphonema micropus</i>
180395	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Mastogloiales	Mastogloiaceae	<i>Mastogloia</i>	<i>Mastogloia binotata</i>
149243	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Melosirales	Melosiraceae	<i>Melosira</i>	<i>Melosira dubia</i>
172442	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Naviculales	Amphipleuraceae	<i>Frustulia</i>	<i>Frustulia rhomboides</i>

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495208	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Naviculales	Naviculaceae	<i>Navicula</i>	<i>Navicula rhynchotella</i>
699392	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Naviculales	Naviculaceae	<i>Navicula</i>	<i>Navicula weissflogii</i>
231884	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Naviculales	Pleurosigmataceae	<i>Pleurosigma</i>	<i>Pleurosigma simonsenii</i>
149528	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Thalassiophysales	Catenulaceae	<i>Amphora</i>	<i>Amphora arenaria</i>
149529	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Thalassiophysales	Catenulaceae	<i>Amphora</i>	<i>Amphora ostrearia</i>
163839	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Thalassiophysales	Catenulaceae	<i>Catenula</i>	<i>Catenula adhaerens</i>
149351	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Triceratiales	Plagiogrammaceae	<i>Plagiogramma</i>	<i>Plagiogramma staurophorum</i>
149329	Heterokontophyta	Bacillariophyceae	Triceratiales	Triceratiaceae	<i>Cerataulus</i>	<i>Cerataulus smithii</i>
563189	Myzozoa	Conoidasida	Eugregarinorida	Selenidiidae	<i>Selenidium</i>	<i>Selenidium serpulae</i>
563196	Myzozoa	Conoidasida	Eugregarinorida	Selenidiidae	<i>Selenidium</i>	<i>Selenidium terebellae</i>
576930	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Amphilothales	Amphilothaceae	<i>Achradina</i>	<i>Achradina sulcata</i>
233712	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Gonyaulacales	Pyrocystaceae	<i>Ostreopsis</i>	<i>Ostreopsis siamensis</i>
109776	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Gymnodiniales	Gymnodiniaceae	<i>Cochlodinium</i>	<i>Cochlodinium vinctum</i>
615516	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Gymnodiniales	Gymnodiniaceae	<i>Sclerodinium</i>	<i>Sclerodinium calyptroglyphe</i>
109898	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Gymnodiniales	Polykrikaceae	<i>Polykrikos</i>	<i>Polykrikos hartmannii</i>
110127	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Peridinales	Oxytoxaceae	<i>Sabulodinium</i>	<i>Sabulodinium undulatum</i>
233835	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Peridinales	Peridiniaceae	<i>Ensiculifera</i>	<i>Ensiculifera carinata</i>
616679	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Peridinales	Peridiniaceae	<i>Lebessphaera</i>	<i>Lebessphaera urania</i>
640321	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Peridinales	Peridinales <i>incertae sedis</i>	<i>Glenodinium</i>	<i>Glenodinium inflatum</i>
110227	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Peridinales	Protoperidiniaceae	<i>Protoperidinium</i>	<i>Protoperidinium islandicum</i>
110242	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Peridinales	Protoperidiniaceae	<i>Protoperidinium</i>	<i>Protoperidinium oviforme</i>
837196	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Peridinales	Protoperidiniaceae	<i>Protoperidinium</i>	<i>Protoperidinium shanghaiense</i>
232348	Myzozoa	Dinophyceae	Prorocentrales	Prorocentraceae	<i>Prorocentrum</i>	<i>Prorocentrum obtusum</i>
577553	Ochrophyta	Chrysophyceae	Chromulinales	Dinobryaceae	<i>Dinobryon</i>	<i>Dinobryon suecicum</i>
574224	Ochrophyta	Dictyochophyceae	Dictyochales	Dictyochaceae	<i>Distephanus</i>	<i>Distephanus octonarius</i>
145447	Ochrophyta	Phaeophyceae	Ectocarpales	Chordariaceae	<i>Mikrosyphar</i>	<i>Mikrosyphar polysiphoniae</i>
1311362	Ochrophyta	Phaeophyceae	Ectocarpales	Scytosiphonaceae	<i>Planosiphon</i>	<i>Planosiphon zosterifolius</i>
145457	Ochrophyta	Phaeophyceae	Ishigeales	Piliniaceae	<i>Pilinia</i>	<i>Pilinia rimosa</i>
145731	Ochrophyta	Phaeophyceae	Laminariales	Laminariaceae	<i>Laminaria</i>	<i>Laminaria solidungula</i>
145296	Ochrophyta	Phaeophyceae	Tilopteridales	Cutleriaceae	<i>Cutleria</i>	<i>Cutleria chilosa</i>
493571	Radiozoa	Polycystina	Nassellaria	Plagiacanthidae	<i>Pseudodictyophimus</i>	<i>Pseudodictyophimus platycephalus</i>
493586	Radiozoa	Polycystina	Nassellaria	Pterocorythidae	<i>Lamprocyclas</i>	<i>Lamprocyclas hannai</i>
413091	Radiozoa	Polycystina	Nassellaria	Theoperidae	<i>Pterocanium</i>	<i>Pterocanium elegans</i>
493315	Radiozoa	Polycystina	Spumellaria	Actinommididae	<i>Cladococcus</i>	<i>Cladococcus cervicornis</i>
Plantae						
146391	Rhodophyta	Florideophyceae	Corallinales	Corallinaceae	<i>Pneophyllum</i>	<i>Pneophyllum coronatum</i>
144406	Rhodophyta	Florideophyceae	Gigartinales	Schmiziellaceae	<i>Schmitziella</i>	<i>Schmitziella endophloea</i>

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145698	Rhodophyta	Florideophyceae	Gracilariales	Gracilariaceae	<i>Gracilaria</i>	<i>Gracilaria dura</i>
494811	Rhodophyta	Florideophyceae	Halymeniales	Halymeniaceae	<i>Cryptonemia</i>	<i>Cryptonemia tuniformis</i>
841097	Rhodophyta	Florideophyceae	Halymeniales	Halymeniaceae	<i>Felicinia</i>	<i>Felicinia marginata</i>
145199	Rhodophyta	Florideophyceae	Hapalidiales	Hapalidiaceae	<i>Phymatolithon</i>	<i>Phymatolithon calcareum</i>
371032	Rhodophyta	Florideophyceae	Hildenbrandiales	Hildenbrandiaceae	<i>Hildenbrandia</i>	<i>Hildenbrandia crouaniorum</i>
145752	Rhodophyta	Florideophyceae	Nemaliales	Liagoraceae	<i>Helminthocladia</i>	<i>Helminthocladia calvadosii</i>
145276	Rhodophyta	Florideophyceae	Peyssonneliales	Peyssonneliaceae	<i>Peyssonnelia</i>	<i>Peyssonnelia coriacea</i>
145795	Tracheophyta	Magnoliopsida	Alismatales	Zosteraceae	<i>Zostera</i>	<i>Zostera marina</i>

